
BREAKING THE SILENCE TRACING THE RISE OF ANTI-ZIONIST SENTIMENT AMONG JEWISH MILLENNIALS AND GEN-Z

Mohamed Buheji

Founder- Socioeconomic Institute for Advanced Studies (SIAS)- Rwanda

Aamir Hasan

Advocate - India

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the evolving stance of young Jewish Millennials and Generation Z toward Zionism and the Israel-Palestine conflict. Historically, Zionism has been widely embraced within Jewish communities as a movement crucial to Jewish identity and security. However, recent years have seen an increasing number of younger Jewish individuals in Israel and the diaspora question, and even oppose, traditional Zionist ideologies. This shift is fueled by growing discomfort with Israel's policies in Palestinian territories, which many young Jews view as inconsistent with values of social justice, equality, and human rights.

Through a mixed-methods approach that includes a review of mainstream and social media content, this study analyzes the factors behind this generational shift, highlighting the role of historical context, educational influences, and increased access to Palestinian perspectives. Prominent voices from within the Jewish community, including intellectuals and activists, reveal a disillusionment with Zionism and a growing alignment with anti-Zionist movements. The paper also explores how these changes are impacting Jewish identity, community dynamics, and global perspectives on the Israel-Palestine conflict. By focusing on the generational divide, this study sheds light on a transformative moment in Jewish engagement with Israel, underscoring increased solidarity with Palestinian rights among young Jews and a rising demand for Palestinian sovereignty.

Keywords: Israel-Palestine conflict, Anti-Zionism, Jewish Millennials, Jewish Gen-Z, Social justice, Young Jews Awakening, Israeli occupation, Generational shift

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1. Introduction

The Israel-Palestine conflict, marked by over a century of political, territorial, and religious disputes, has long influenced Jewish identity and perspectives on Zionism within Israel and the global Jewish diaspora. Initially, the Zionist movement sought to establish a safe homeland for Jews in Israel, driven by historical ties to the land and a response to centuries of anti-Semitism and persecution. For decades, Zionism was widely embraced within Jewish communities as a movement tied to Jewish security, identity, and survival. However, in recent years, there has been a noticeable shift, particularly among younger Jewish generations, as they increasingly question and even oppose traditional Zionist ideologies.

This shift stems from a growing discomfort among Millennials and Gen-Z with Israel's ongoing occupation of Palestinian territories and the implications of these policies on Palestinian human rights and freedoms, Buheji (2024b). Many younger Jews, both in Israel and abroad, now view these actions as inconsistent with the values of social justice, equality, and human rights. Access to information through social media and global activism has exposed this generation to Palestinian narratives and fostered a reexamination of the historical and political assumptions surrounding Zionism. As a result, an anti-Zionist stance, once marginalized within Jewish discourse, is gaining prominence among young Jews who feel morally compelled to speak out against what they perceive as systemic oppression. Buheji (2024a)

This paper explores this generational shift within the Jewish community toward anti-Zionism, examining the historical context, educational influences, and sociopolitical factors that contribute to this changing perspective. It highlights the voices of young Jewish individuals and intellectuals who challenge the narratives of Zionism and advocate for Palestinian rights, Buheji (2024a). Furthermore, it investigates the impact of this shift on Jewish identity, community relations, and the broader discourse on Israel and Palestine. Through this exploration, the paper aims to shed light on the evolving landscape of Jewish identity and activism, underscoring a transformative moment in Jewish engagement with the Israel-Palestine conflict.

2.0 Methodology

Based on the literature review, the authors have extensively reviewed the websites, major news stream media and the social media channels on the changing views of the people of Israel on Zionism and towards the people of Palestine. This study will employ a mixed-methods approach to analyze news dissemination and framing across social media and mainstream media platforms. It will combine qualitative content analysis to understand narrative patterns and framing techniques with quantitative analysis to examine news coverage's volume, reach, and sentiment.

The researchers selected major social media platforms (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, Instagram) and mainstream media outlets (e.g., major news websites and newspapers) that are relevant to the study topic. The researchers identified a timeframe of two months of, September and October 2024, for the data collection. They used systematic sampling to gather relevant posts, articles, and broadcasts related to the topic. Social media data will be collected using API tools, while mainstream media content will be gathered through news databases or monitoring software.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Background of the Israeli War on Gaza

The Israel-Palestine conflict has become increasingly complex due to its historical roots and the multifaceted disputes spanning religious, territorial, and ethnic dimensions (Smith, 2013). The conflict traces back over 80 years, beginning with the Zionist movement's efforts to establish Jewish settlements in Palestine, while Arab nations were seeking freedom from the Ottoman Empire. The Balfour Declaration in 1917 advanced the notion of a Jewish homeland in Palestine, marking the beginning of significant Palestinian displacement and occupation (Balfour, 1970). These developments escalated tensions, and the Israeli-Palestinian conflict came to be recognized as one of the most intense conflicts of the 20th century (Shlaim, 1996).

In 1948, around 750,000 Palestinians were displaced, and approximately 78 per cent of Palestinian land fell under Israeli control. By 1967, Israel had extended its control over the West Bank and Gaza, maintaining a dominant stance over Palestinians. Many argue that Israel's colonization policies, including establishing Jewish settlements and demolishing Palestinian homes, aim to displace Palestinians and claim land. Such policies have led to widespread displacement and have increasingly alienated younger Jewish individuals, many of whom disapprove of these occupation tactics. Chehata (2015), Al-Jazeera English (2024a).

3.2 Israeli Mindset and Regional Dynamics

Israel perceives itself as less powerful compared to neighbouring Arab states but more powerful in relation to Palestinians (Rouhana & Fiske, 1995). Events such as European anti-Semitism, the Holocaust, and the United Nations' partition of Palestine in 1948 have influenced Israel's stance on security and self-preservation. In 1948, Palestine was divided into Jewish and Arab states, with Israel obtaining more territory than initially proposed. This division led to Israel's founding and subsequent wars, with Israel emerging victorious and expanding its territory (Pappe, 2001).

3.3 Displacement and the Jewish Settlement Project

The Zionist movement initially considered locations beyond Palestine, such as Western Australia and Uganda, for Jewish settlement (Avineri, 1981). However, historical and biblical associations with Palestine led to its selection as the Jewish homeland, despite alternative proposals. Zionism as a political movement grew out of this decision, advocating Jewish nationalistic claims over Palestine. Some supporters argue that Zionism connects Jewish people to the land of Israel; however, critics, including certain groups within the Jewish community, claim that Zionism often undermines Palestinian rights (Sand, 2009; Tanjim, 2023).

Zionism has also fostered distinctions among Jewish groups in Israel. Ashkenazim, descendants of European immigrants, and Mizrahim, Middle Eastern Jews, have culturally different identities, with Mizrahim sharing closer cultural ties to Arabs (Shenhav, 2002). These internal divisions highlight the complex socio-cultural makeup of Israel, influenced by various strands of Jewish identity and ideology.

3.4 Global Criticism and the Uprise of Anti-Zionism

Anti-Zionism opposes Israeli policies and advocates Palestinian rights. Critics equate Zionism with racial discrimination, and anti-Zionist movements view the ideology as a force preventing Palestinian self-determination. The rise of anti-Zionism after the events of October 7 has drawn attention to Israel's occupation policies and their impact on Palestinian lives (Christ, 2024).

Some intellectuals argue that criticism of Israel's state policies is a universal right. Such criticism, they argue, stems from concerns about Israel's treatment of Palestinians and the expansion of settlements, which some view as violations of international law. As Israel faces increasing international scrutiny, the impact of its policies on Palestinian sovereignty remains a central issue (Christ, 2024).

4. The Case of Young Jews Generation Awakening

4.1 The "Brainwashing" Project in Jewish Schools and Rising Disillusionment

In Jewish educational institutions, Israel is often presented as integral to Jewish identity, a belief reinforced by programs that send students to Israel and emphasize Zionist ideology. Rabbi Bennett Miller highlights how students return with stronger Zionist beliefs, linking Israel directly with Jewish heritage (Al-Jazeera English, 2024a). However, there is a growing disillusionment, particularly among Jewish millennials, who feel disconnected from Israel's policies and actions. Figures like Abe Foxman, from the Anti-Defamation League, note increased efforts to reinforce Zionist ideals as more young people become critical of Israel (Al-Jazeera English, 2024a). Sarah Annie Minkin, of the Foundation for Middle East Peace, argues that anti-Semitism is being used to justify continued U.S. support for Israel, often prioritizing state interests over Jewish safety.

4.2 How Jewish Millennials and Gen-Z are Discovering the Palestinian Experience of Confinement under a Military Occupation

Recent studies indicate a notable rise in anti-Zionist sentiment among Jewish Millennials and Generation Z. A 2022 survey revealed that when Zionism was defined as "the belief in privileging Jewish rights over non-Jewish rights in Israel," 69% of American Jews identified as probably or definitely not Zionist. Additionally, a 2024 Anti-Defamation League (ADL) survey found that Millennials agree with an average of 5.37 anti-Jewish tropes, followed by Generation Z at 5.01, indicating a shift in perspectives within these age groups. These findings suggest a growing trend among younger Jewish individuals toward questioning or opposing traditional Zionist ideologies. Iqbal (2024)

For Palestinians, daily life in occupied territories resembles confinement, with freedom remaining largely out of reach. Avner Gvarya, executive director of Breaking the Silence, recounts his experiences as an Israeli soldier, including unrestricted access to Palestinian homes and the ability to detain residents without warrants. Gvarya later viewed these actions with shame and noted that an American visitor to the occupied territories would have more rights than a Palestinian living there (Al-Jazeera English, 2024a). Peter Beinart, editor-at-large of Jewish Currents, also highlights how Palestinians in occupied areas live without citizenship rights, under a system that effectively denies them political representation and legal equality.

This system has led some, such as Lara Friedman, president of the Foundation for Middle East Peace, to describe it as an apartheid system, with Palestinians subjected to different laws than Israelis. Human rights lawyer Noura Erakat and filmmaker Rebecca Pierce argue that the situation represents a form of colonization and apartheid. Pierce noted that her perspective on the issue shifted after crossing a checkpoint in Bethlehem, where the visible division altered her views on Israeli policies (Al-Jazeera English, 2024a).

According to Anthony Loewenstein, a Jewish German Australian citizen who had regular visits to Gaza and enjoyed the hospitality there, things changed after 7th October 2023. In his book "The Palestine Laboratory", Anthony Lowenstein (2024) compares Palestine as a testing ground for the weapons manufactured by Israel, testing them on Palestinians in Palestine and then exporting them all across the world.

4.3 Moral Awakening and Advocacy Among Young Jews and Intellectuals

Jewish Millennials and Generation Z are increasingly viewing Israel's actions through a framework of social justice and human rights, voicing their discomfort with what they see as systemic injustices toward Palestinians. Dr. Cornel West, a professor at Union Theological Seminary, observes a "moral awakening" among young Jews, many of whom feel a strong sense of responsibility to advocate for Palestinian rights. Noam Chomsky also notes that Israel is aware of this shift, recognizing that committed activism from young Jewish voices could bring about significant change. Congresswoman Rashida Tlaib condemns the situation in Israel as an "apartheid regime," asserting that it strips Palestinians of dignity (Al-Jazeera English, 2024a).

Iqbal (2024) after the Jewish Voice for Peace (JVP) how it is becoming is developing progressively as a Jewish anti-Zionist organisation in the world - more Jewish Americans, both young and old, "are anti-Zionist (more) than ever before. This moral stance is echoed by Israeli academics and activists. Oren Yiftachel, a professor of political geography at Ben-Gurion University, has criticized Israel's apartheid policies and advocates for a one-state solution that could provide equal rights for Israelis and Palestinians (Yiftachel, 2006). Similarly, Jeff Halper, an anthropologist and head of the Israeli Committee Against House Demolitions, has been arrested multiple times for his efforts to prevent Palestinian home demolitions, building houses for Palestinians as an act of solidarity (Chehata, 2015). Eitan Bronstein Aparico, a former Israeli army officer and now an anti-Zionist activist living in Brussels, believes that Israel's apartheid system will eventually come to an end (Aparico, 2019).

Among other Israeli intellectuals, there is a growing belief in a single-state solution as the only viable path for peaceful coexistence. Meron Benvenisti, an Israeli political scientist, argues that a single-state framework may be essential for Israel's survival (Roberts, 2020). Author and novelist Dorit Rabinyan's banned novel **All the Rivers**, which portrays a romance between an Israeli woman and a Palestinian man, highlights the tension around Israeli censorship and cultural suppression (Stenberg, 2017). Other prominent voices like Gilad Atzmon, a jazz musician based in the UK, have criticized the U.S. for obstructing Palestinian efforts to gain recognition at the United Nations (Anadolu Ajansi, 2014).

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Iqbal (2024) narrate after Rachel Liberty, a spokesperson for IfNotNow (INN) NYC - an American Jewish group that opposes Israel's occupation of Palestine, that more Jews refuse to accept giving Israel unconditional military support and financial aid. INN and similar organization have seen a wave of support amongst young Jews in the US for a permanent ceasefire and liberation of Palestine.

This wave of dissent among young Israelis and Jewish intellectuals is reflected in rising protests against illegal Israeli settlements in the West Bank. Figures such as Jonathan Pollak, an Israeli graphic designer, and Dr. Stavit Sinai, a sociologist and product of Israel's Zionist education system, have joined protests. Sinai, raised by a Holocaust-surviving family, now believes that Israel's policies deprive Palestinians of freedom and liberty, operating under an imperialist and apartheid framework (Lenkinski, 2023).

Others take a more radical stance, like Ronnie Barkan, who controversially describes Zionism as a "mental disorder" that prevents Israelis from seeing Palestinians as equal human beings (Real Media, 2024). Michael Ofer Ziv, an Israeli army reservist, refused to serve in Gaza after witnessing the suffering of Palestinian civilians (Al-Jazeera English, 2024b; Saifi, 2024). Elijah Kahlenberg, a Jewish student at the University of Texas, asserts that Israeli education promotes anti-Palestinian sentiment and fails to teach about the Nakba. He also criticizes corporations profiting from the Israeli-Palestinian conflict (Al-Jazeera English, 2024c).

The criticism extends to Jewish activists abroad, such as Naomi Klein, a Canadian author who denounced Zionism at a protest in New York (Middle East Eye, 2024). Individuals supporting Palestinian rights have faced significant backlash, including job losses and legal repercussions. For instance, Mir Baruchin, a teacher, was imprisoned and fired for posting pro-Palestinian content online, although he was later reinstated (Minisini, 2024). Dan Fischer, a Hebrew teacher in Indiana, and other Jewish professionals in the U.S. were dismissed from their positions after expressing solidarity with Gaza (Burley, 2024). In Illinois, an educator was fired for sharing a video by a Palestinian comedian, and in New England, a rabbi was dismissed for promoting a ceasefire song (Burley, 2024; Brown, 2024; Buheji et al., 2024).

Together, these voices illustrate a growing movement of young Jews and intellectuals advocating for Palestinian rights and challenging traditional Zionist ideologies. This generational shift reflects a broader moral awakening as young Jews align their values of social justice and human rights with active support for Palestinian sovereignty and equality.

Figure (1) Shows Young Jews who are Facing the Genocide in Gaza.

Source: Burely (2024) <https://inthesetimes.com/article/anti-zionist-israel-gaza-jewish-institutions>

4.4 Fractures in Israeli Society and Calls for Palestinian Sovereignty

Israeli society is increasingly divided, especially regarding its policies on Palestine and Gaza. This division is evident among Israeli dissidents, who often face suppression within a predominantly Zionist society. Some Israelis, feeling their democratic values threatened by controversial judicial reforms, have even chosen to emigrate (Cordall, 2024). According to *The Guardian*, Zionists make up about 40 percent of the Israeli army, while orthodox Jews show minimal interest in military service, illustrating further internal divides.

The growing demand for Palestinian sovereignty is being voiced not only by international allies but also by young Jews advocating for Israel to dismantle its apartheid wall, withdraw from occupied territories, and allow displaced Palestinians to return home. This call for change reflects a global shift in favor of Palestinian rights, highlighting the need for long-term engagement from all stakeholders to achieve meaningful progress.

Individual accounts from Israelis and diaspora Jews illustrate the personal struggles and changing perspectives regarding Israel's policies. Etan, an Israeli army veteran raised in Atlanta, Georgia, recalls his journey from early Zionist fervor to moral disillusionment. As a child, he admired the Western Wall and dreamed of living in Israel. His summer camps included midnight military simulations, sparking a lifelong ambition to join the army. Deployed in the West Bank after rigorous training, Etan was responsible for ID checks and security but began to question his role after witnessing the brutal treatment of a young Palestinian detainee. This incident marked a turning point, leading him to see even routine actions, like stopping Palestinians at checkpoints, as morally troubling (Buheji, 2024b; Al-Jazeera English, 2024a).

Simmon Zimmerman, co-founder of *IfNotNow* at the University of California, Berkeley, shares a similar shift in perspective. Raised in a Jewish school and having visited Israel during high school, Zimmerman initially felt connected to Israel and saw it as central to her Jewish identity. In Israel, she participated in army simulations and attended AIPAC events, feeling part of a supportive community. However, her views changed as she began to recognize the hardships Palestinians face, including restricted access to necessities like water and power. The interactions with Palestinian students who described Israel's actions as colonial and apartheid deeply impacted Simmon, however, this made her lose friends and family members due to her activism, facing backlash from her community for standing with Palestinians (Al-Jazeera English, 2024a).

At the University of Connecticut, Hillel fellow Tom Barkan emphasizes that serving in the Israeli army is considered a way of supporting Israel. However, perspectives like those of Palestinian tour guide Baha Hilo and activist Sami Awad present a starkly different view. Hilo, having returned to Palestine from the U.S., believes that understanding the impact of Israeli policies on Palestinians requires living among them. Awad, executive director of the Holy Land Trust and a U.S. citizen born in Bethlehem, recalls the trauma of displacement during the 1948 war, which saw approximately 750,000 Palestinians evacuated and 78 percent of Palestinian land occupied. Awad describes Israel's ongoing dominance, including the takeover of the West Bank and Gaza in 1967, as part of a broader colonial project. He recounts instances where Jewish settlers threw stones, chemicals, or dead animals when his team attempted to repair Palestinian wells or collect rainwater, actions he sees as symbolic of the deeper struggle over land and sovereignty.

4.5 Israeli Citizens Leaving Israel Due to War in Gaza

The recent war in Gaza has triggered a significant increase in Israeli emigration, with citizens leaving due to safety and security concerns. A report from *Middle East Monitor* highlights a 285 per cent rise in Israelis permanently leaving the country following the October 7, 2023 conflict, with the Population and Immigration Authority of Israel reporting that nearly 500,000 Israelis have emigrated since that date (Middle East Monitor, 2024; Sio, 2023). This exodus reflects not only fears surrounding immediate threats but also deeper political and social tensions within Israeli society.

One factor driving this migration is the controversial judicial reform implemented by the Israeli government, which has raised concerns about the erosion of democratic values. Dissidents have expressed that they no longer wish to live in a country where their rights are not protected and where ultra-Orthodox political influence threatens civil liberties (BBC News, 2023). Prominent Israeli journalist Gideon Levy addresses these issues in his book, *The Killing of Gaza: Reports on a Catastrophe*, where he discusses how Israeli citizens are often led to perceive Palestinians as inherently hostile. Levy argues that this narrative reinforces a cycle of fear and mistrust within Israeli society (Levy, 2024).

Additionally, an analysis in *Forward*, a Jewish newspaper, emphasizes that the October 7 attack was not the only factor prompting people to leave; internal political divisions and societal instability have also driven long-standing emigration considerations (Greene, 2024). Political analyst Shwrmine Narwani refers to this trend as a “reverse Aliyah,” where Jews are leaving Israel in unprecedented numbers. She suggests that Israel’s foundational stability is under severe strain, stating metaphorically that “both of its legs are broken.” Reflecting this shift, applications for Portuguese citizenship among Israelis have surged to 21,000 since 2023, as many look for alternative places of residence (Amer, 2023).

These patterns of emigration reveal a society grappling with profound ideological and security challenges, with implications for Israel’s demographic and political future as its citizens seek safety, stability, and democratic integrity elsewhere.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 The Clear Disenchantment with the Zionist Project

This paper went through clear factors that collectively contribute to the growing disenchantment among Jewish Millennials and Gen Z with Israel, reflecting broader generational shifts in values, identity, and global perspectives. The findings of this study reveal a significant generational shift within Jewish communities regarding views on Zionism and the Israel-Palestine conflict. The emerging anti-Zionist sentiment among younger Jewish generations reflects a broader rethinking of Jewish identity, one increasingly shaped by values of social justice and human rights rather than nationalism alone. Many Millennials and Gen Z Jews, in Israel and globally, are re-examining traditional Zionist narratives as they confront the realities of occupation and systemic inequality faced by Palestinians.

One of the main reasons for disenchantment among the current young Jewish generations in the diaspora is that they are now directly taking the news from social media from those suffering the genocide in Gaza, and they are inspiring the world with their values, persistence and resilience to their cause.

Through social media and global activism, younger Jews have gained access to Palestinian voices, challenging the perspectives ingrained in Zionist education and leading to a sense of moral and ethical responsibility toward Palestinian rights. This generational shift has profound implications for the Jewish community. As more young Jews vocalize anti-Zionist views, tensions within Jewish communities are growing, particularly between older Zionists and younger anti-Zionists. The internal divide is further influenced by the sociopolitical climate in Israel, where government policies on Gaza, settlement expansion, and judicial reforms add complexity to Jewish identity and solidarity. Additionally, the rise of anti-Zionist sentiment among young Jews has implications for Israel's international relations, potentially affecting its support among diaspora communities, especially in the United States, where Jewish support has traditionally been strong.

These shifts underscore a growing solidarity with Palestinians among Jewish youth, which aligns with global human rights movements. The debate around Zionism, anti-Zionism, and Jewish identity points to a transformative moment in Jewish discourse, as young Jews increasingly advocate for policies they believe align with ethical and universal human rights values.

5.2 The Need to Sustain the Exposure of the Palestinian Narrative Among the Young Jewish Community in the East and the West

The generational shift within Jewish communities, particularly among Millennials and Gen Z, reflects a significant departure from traditional Zionist ideologies that have historically defined Jewish identity and solidarity with Israel. The study reveals that young Jewish individuals are increasingly critical of Israel's policies toward Palestinians, with many identifying as anti-Zionists and rejecting narratives that prioritize nationalism over social justice. This shift is fueled by exposure to Palestinian narratives, access to global activism, and educational experiences that prompt ethical questions about Israel's treatment of Palestinians.

The impact of this shift is highly important for the Free Palestine movement. This awakening not only addresses the ideological divides between traditional Jewish Zionist institutions but also makes these youth advocates for Palestinian sovereignty. This paper highlights and foresight a pivotal change in Jewish engagement with the Israel-Palestine conflict, suggesting that the future of Jewish identity may increasingly center around universal human rights and social justice values. As the global discourse on Israel and Palestine continues to evolve, the influence of young Jewish voices calling for justice and equity is likely to play a critical role in shaping future dialogue and policy on this complex issue.

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